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Factores que afectan la percepción de los estudiantes de secundaria sobre la profesión de trabajo social en el Delta del Mekong Vietnamita: un estudio de caso en la Provincia de Dong Thap

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Resumen: El artículo identifica los factores que afectan la percepción de la profesión de trabajo social entre los estudiantes de secundaria y las diferencias entre estos factores según las características demográficas en las escuelas secundarias de la Provincia de Dong Thap. El estudio construyó una escala que comprende 25 variables observables a través de una encuesta aleatoria a 270 estudiantes de secundaria para evaluar el nivel de influencia en la percepción de la profesión de trabajo social. Los hallazgos muestran que hay tres factores que influyen en la percepción de los estudiantes sobre la profesión de trabajo social: el factor personal, las características específicas de la profesión y la influencia de la familia, amigos y maestros. El nivel medio de influencia en el factor personal es el más alto con 3.09 (DE=0.72), seguido por el puntaje medio del factor de influencia de la familia, amigos y maestros con 3.02 (DE=0.70), y el puntaje medio más bajo es para las características específicas de la profesión de trabajo social con 2.99 (DE=0.71). Además, indican diferencias en los puntajes medios de los factores de influencia, con las estudiantes obteniendo puntajes más altos que los estudiantes, y los estudiantes que estudian la carrera de Ciencias Sociales teniendo puntajes medios más altos en los factores de influencia en comparación con los estudiantes que estudian la carrera de Ciencias Naturales ($p < 0.05$). Los hallazgos proporcionaron una base para que las escuelas diseñen programas de orientación y asesoramiento profesional para los estudiantes de manera más adecuada y efectiva.

Palabras clave: percepción, profesión de trabajo social, estudiantes de secundaria, Delta del Mekong vietnamita, Provincia de Dong Thap.

Factors affecting high school students' perception of social work profession in the Vietnamese Mekong Delta: a case study in Dong Thap Province

Abstract. The article identifies the factors that affect the perception of the social work profession among high school students and the differences between these factors according to demographic characteristics in high schools in Dong Thap Province. The study built a scale comprising 25 observable variables through a random survey of 270 high school students to assess the level of influence on the perception of the social work profession. The findings show that there are three factors that influence students' perception of the social work profession: the personal factor, the specific characteristics of the profession, and the influence of family, friends, and teachers. The average level of influence in the personal factor is the highest at 3.09 (SD = 0.72), followed by the average score of the influence factor of family, friends, and teachers at 3.02 (SD = 0.70), and the lowest average score is for the specific characteristics of the social work profession at 2.99 (SD = 0.71). In addition, differences in the average scores of the influencing factors are indicated, with female students obtaining higher scores than male students, and students studying the Social Sciences major having higher average scores in the influencing factors compared to students studying the Natural Sciences major ($p < 0.05$). The findings provided a basis for schools to design career guidance and counseling programs for students in a more appropriate and effective way.

Keywords: perception; social work profession, high school students, Vietnamese Mekong Delta, Dong Thap Province.

INTRODUCTION

Social work is a scientific and professional field aimed at assisting vulnerable individuals, groups, and communities to address difficult issues, focusing on human interaction with the social environment, thereby enhancing their problem-solving abilities and adaptability in life. This profession has assisted various vulnerable groups in society such as children, the elderly, women, people with disabilities, and has applications in areas such as family, schools, hospitals, and social welfare (Jones & Truell, 2012).

Globally, the field of social work has developed in Europe and the Americas and has evolved into a professional occupation in developed countries for over a century. In Vietnam, the field of social work was established later compared to developed countries and has only been shaped through legal assistance systems and social policies since the reform period in 1986 (Bui, 2012; H. H. Nguyen, 2018). In order to develop social work into a professional occupation, fulfill the mission of helping people enhance resilience abilities and problem-solving skills, connect people to access support resources and social services to improve their quality of life, and bring about sustainable and harmonious development between individuals and social environment, the Prime Minister of Vietnam signed Decision No. 32/2010/QĐ-TTg approving the scheme on the development of the Social work profession during 2010-2020,

marking an important milestone for the social work profession in Vietnam with the goal: “Develop social work into a profession in Vietnam; enhance social awareness of the social work profession; build a sufficient quantity of social work officers, civil servants, employees, and collaborators meeting quality requirements, linked to the development of social work service delivery systems at all levels, contributing to the construction of an advanced social welfare system” (Prime Minister of Vietnam, 2010). The main goal of the project is to develop social work into a professional occupation in Vietnam, wherein raising societal awareness of the social work profession is one of its key objectives. However, in the current context, it is evident that many people still do not understand the social work profession. A significant portion of public opinion still confuses and equates social work with charitable activities, lacking comprehensive understanding of the function, role, and purpose of providing social services, which serve as tools to convey social policies to the people within the social welfare system of the social work profession (H. H. Nguyen, 2015; T. H. Nguyen, 2014). This issue has become a major barrier in training social work personnel to meet social needs, especially influencing career orientation in social work for high school students in current educational institutions.

Understanding a profession among students often depends on various factors, particularly those related to future career choices. For high school students, career selection is a top priority and the most significant decision for graduating students, as it profoundly influences their future (T. X. T. Le, 2015). Choosing a profession is a decisive process for students, especially in a relatively new field like social work where students’ perception of the profession is crucial and influenced by many factors. Based on a synthesis of several studies on the factors influencing students’ perception and career choices, three fundamental factors emerge: (a) Intrinsic factors (personal preferences, individual characteristics such as personality, appearance, and job satisfaction) (Karaca et al., 2016); (b) Extrinsic factors (salary, job opportunities, social status, advancement opportunities) (Agarwala, 2008); (c) Influence from surroundings (family members’ occupations, family guidance, teacher advice, and peer influence) (Alyafei, 2018; Carpenter & Foster, 1977). Identifying the factors influencing perception of the social work profession is essential and crucial to assist schools and families in providing appropriate support, guidance, and counseling to help students make informed decisions regarding their future career choices in this field.

In recent years, the situation of social work specialization training at university education institutions has provided evidence for the aforementioned issue. A considerable number of students, upon beginning their studies in social work at university institutions, feel unsuitable, leading to frustration and a desire to switch to other majors. Some students have even dropped out after a period of study due to feeling that the profession does not align with their abilities and aspirations. This reality has significantly impacted the quality of social work human resources training at university education institutions in Vietnam (Mai et al., 2023).

One of the main reasons we believe is the primary impact is the vague and intuitive perception of high school students about the social work profession. It is imperative and urgent to enhance communication efforts and increase students’ understanding before they actually choose to study this profession. Furthermore, it helps students to carefully consider before deciding to commit themselves to a specific profession. Therefore, this study is conducted with the aim of identifying the factors influencing high school students’ perception of the social work profession, while also explor-

ing the correlation between these influencing factors and the demographic factors of high school students in Dong Thap Province. The research findings serve as a basis for proposing suitable career counseling solutions to enhance the perception of the social work profession among high school students in the coming time.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data Collection

This research was carried out using a cross-sectional descriptive method through a random survey of 270 high school students from grade 10 to grade 12 in high schools in Dong Thap Province participating in the survey process and fully answering the questions in the form of self-filling on the questionnaires. Among the 270 surveyed high school students, each grade level and gender group had 90 participants. There was not a significant difference in participation rates between the two gender groups, with 133 male students participating, accounting for 49.3%, and 137 female students participating, accounting for 50.7%.

Research Design

The research was carried out through a survey questionnaire, with the questionnaire information pre-designed and delivered to the students for self-response. Before distributing the pre-designed self-completion questionnaires, the investigators introduced the students to the purpose of the study, while also explaining certain terms such as occupational perception, the social work profession, and factors influencing perception of the profession. During the questionnaire completion process, students were arranged to sit individually at separate desks, and the researchers directly supervised the students' completion of the questionnaires and addressed any queries the students had while responding to the questions.

The questions about consultation demand of students are designed on a 5-point Likert scale, with values ranging from 1 to 5, of which 1 as "absolutely not influential", 2 as "not influential", 3 as "neutral", 4 as "influential", and 5 as "strongly influential".

The research will be conducted after obtaining approval from the School Board. Students participating in the study will be clearly briefed on the purpose and content of the research, emphasizing anonymity and data security.

Data Analysis

The collected data will be entered and processed using the statistical software SPSS version 26. Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient will be employed to examine the correlation coefficient and relationships among variables. Adhering to Cronbach's Alpha rule and assessing internal consistency, $\alpha > 0.9$ indicates excellent reliability, $0.8 < \alpha < 0.9$ signifies good reliability, $0.7 < \alpha < 0.8$ implies acceptable reliability, $0.6 < \alpha < 0.7$ suggests poor reliability, and $\alpha < 0.6$ is considered unacceptable. After testing the reliability of the scales, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) will be conducted to explore which scales are suitable for the structure of the problem under investigation. In the EFA, variables with factor loadings above 0.5 will be retained (Hair, 2010), and the cumulative variance extracted should be greater than 50% (Gerbing & Anderson, 1988). The influencing factor groups will be calculated for mean

scores. Additionally, the study will utilize T-test and ANOVA to compare the differences in mean scores of factors across gender and Basic Sciences, Social Sciences or Natural Sciences fields among high school students.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistical results

The study presented 25 observable variables using a 5-point Likert scale (absolutely not influential, not influential, neutral, influential, strongly influential) for students to assess which criteria had the most impact on them under the form of rating from 1 to 5. Subsequently, we calculated the mean score for each criterion. The results in Table 1 show that the criterion “*You want to help others*” was rated as having the most influence by students with an mean score of 3.17. Next, the criteria “*Self-interest in participating in social activities*” and “*Personality, competence align with the professional requirements of social work*” were both rated as having the second-highest influence with an mean score of 3.12. The criterion “*Parents, relatives, family members work in the field of social work and influence you*” was rated as having the second-lowest mean score of 2.92, and the criterion “*Physical appearance and physique are not suitable for other professions*” was rated as having the lowest mean score of 2.85.

TABLE 1. Description of the mean values of factors influencing the perception of the social work profession among high school students in the study area

Observable Variables	N	Mean	SD
Q.1. Self-interest in participating in social activities.	270	3.05	0.897
Q.2. Self has passion, interest in the field of social work.	270	3.12	0.845
Q.3. Personality, competence align with the professional requirements of social work.	270	3.12	0.880
Q.4. Oneself thinks that this profession is charity, volunteering.	270	3.01	0.871
Q.5. You want to help others.	270	3.17	0.910
Q.6. Want to affirm self-worth, contribute to society.	270	3.10	0.890
Q.7. Physical and appearance are not suitable for other professions.	270	2.85	0.921
Q.8. Parents, relatives, family members work in the field of social work and influence you.	270	2.92	0.865
Q.9. Friends, acquaintances are studying in the social work field, and they influence you.	270	3.02	0.853
Q.10. Friends, acquaintances are working in the social work field, and they influence you.	270	2.97	0.864
Q.11. Impact of career guidance programs on media, social networks.	270	3.09	0.822
Q.12. Impact of Youth Union activities, local associations where you live.	270	3.07	0.796
Q.13. Impact of charity activities you have known or participated in.	270	3.08	0.830

TABLE 1. Continuación

Observable Variables	N	Mean	SD
Q.14. Admiration for a specific individual model who is working effectively in the field of social work.	270	3.00	0.845
Q.15. Teachers inform you about the social work profession.	270	3.04	0.863
Q.16. Friends inform you about the social work profession.	270	3.03	0.822
Q.17. Through school career counseling sessions.	270	3.04	0.861
Q.18. Studying social work is easy to find employment after graduation.	270	2.98	0.890
Q.19. Studying social work can work in many different fields.	270	3.04	0.853
Q.20. Studying social work can work in international non-governmental organizations.	270	3.03	0.847
Q.21. This is a new, interesting field to explore.	270	3.06	0.845
Q.22. This field belongs to the social group so it is not difficult to learn.	270	2.94	0.869
Q.23. This field is receiving attention from the state so there are many development opportunities after graduation.	270	3.02	0.783
Q.24. Lack of information about the profession, field of study, training schools and job opportunities in social work.	270	3.04	0.866
Q.25. Not knowing society has this profession.	270	3.00	0.856

Preliminary assessment of the scale by Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient

The scale "*Factors influencing high school students' perceptions of social work profession*" consists of 3 components and 25 measurement variables. The results of the reliability analysis of the scale all yielded good results, with all measurement variables above 0.3. Therefore, with the 25 variables included in the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), all scale components had Cronbach's Alpha coefficients >0.6, meeting the requirements.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

The results of the factor analysis on the 25 observed variables measuring the influencing factors were grouped into 3 factor groups: individual factors, factors specific to the social work profession, and factors influenced by family, friends, and teachers.

TABLE 2. Eigenvalues

Component	Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative Variance (%)
I (Individual Factors)	14.907	59.627	59.627
II (Factors Specific to Social Work Profession)	1.769	7.078	66.705
III (Factors Influenced by Family, Friends, Teachers)	1.105	4.422	71.126

From the statistical results in Table 2, Factor 1 (consisting of 8 sub-items) explains 59.627% of the variance in the scale, Factor 2 (consisting of 9 sub-items) explains 7.078% of the variance, and Factor 3 (consisting of 8 sub-items) explains 4.422% of the variance. In total, the 3 factors explain 71.126% of the variance in the scale.

TABLE 3. Correlation values of observable variables and Cronbach's Alpha values of Influencing factors

Factors and Observable variables	Correlation values of Observable variables		
	I	II	III
I. Individual Factors			
Q.3. Your personality and abilities are suitable for the professional requirements of social work.	0.820		
Q.2. Self has passion, interest in the field of social work.	0.819		
Q.5. You want to help others.	0.816		
Q.1. You enjoy participating in social activities.	0.792		
Q.6. You want to affirm your self-worth and contribute to society.	0.628		
Q.17. Through school career counseling sessions.	0.612		
Q.11. The impact of career guidance programs on various media and social networks.	0.536		
Q.4. Oneself thinks that this profession is charity, volunteering.	0.533		
<i>Cronbach's Alpha value (8 observable variables)</i>	0.930		
II. Factors Specific to Social Work Profession			
Q.19. Social work studies can lead to employment in various fields.	0.760		
Q.24. Lack of information about the profession, field of study, training institutions, and job opportunities in social work.	0.759		
Q.22. This field belongs to the social sciences, so it is not difficult to learn.	0.716		
Q.23. This field is receiving attention from the government, hence, there are many development opportunities after graduation.	0.698		
Q.21. This is a new, interesting field to explore.	0.693		
Q.25. Not knowing society has this profession.	0.638		
Q.18. Social work studies make it easy to find employment after graduation.	0.637		
Q.20. Social work studies can lead to work in international non-governmental organizations.	0.631		
Q.7. Physical appearance and physique are not suitable for other professions.	0.564		
<i>Cronbach's Alpha value (9 observable variables)</i>	0.942		
III. Factors Influenced by Family, Friends, Teachers			
Q.10. Friends, acquaintances are working in the social work field, and they influence you.	0.830		
Q.9. Friends, acquaintances are studying in the social work field, and they influence you.	0.787		
Q.8. Parents, relatives, family members work in the field of social work and influence you.	0.723		
Q.12. Impact of Youth Union activities, local associations where you live.	0.625		
Q.16. Friends inform you about the social work profession.	0.610		
Q.13. The influence of charity activities you have known or participated in.	0.600		
Q.14. Admiring a specific individual who is effectively working in the field of social work.	0.531		
Q.15. Teachers inform you about the social work profession.	0.505		
<i>Cronbach's Alpha value (8 observable variables)</i>	0.937		
<i>Cronbach's Alpha value for the entire scale (25 observable variables) = 0.971.</i>			

The reliability of the scale was assessed through internal consistency using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for each factor and for the entire scale. According to the statistical results in Table 3, the scale measuring factors influencing the perception of social work profession consists of 3 factors with Cronbach's alpha values as follows: Factor 1 = 0.930, Factor 2 = 0.942, Factor 3 = 0.937 (all reaching good levels), and the overall scale reliability = 0.971 (reaching a good level) (Cicchetti et al., 2011; Müller & Büttner, 1994). The results indicate that the tool demonstrates good internal consistency according to the literature in social science research (Müller & Büttner, 1994).

Verification of the differences between factors influencing the perception of Social work profession and socio-demographic factors of high school students

The logical validity of the tool was analyzed by comparing the mean scores of factors influencing the perception of social work profession across different groups based on gender and academic level. In this study, the mean scores of factors influencing the perception of social work profession were calculated as the mean scores of the variables constituting each factor. The mean score for the individual factor was 3.09 (SD=0.72, ranging from 1-5). The mean score for the factor specific to the social work profession was 2.99 (SD=0.71, ranging from 1-5). The mean score for the family, friends, and teachers factor was 3.02 (SD=0.70, ranging from 1-5).

TABLE 4. Mean values of factors influencing perception of Social work profession by gender

Factors	Male	Female	p-value
Mean values of individual factor	2.99 (SD = 0.74)	3.17 (SD = 0.68)	0.044
Mean values of profession-specific factor	2.89 (SD = 0.72)	3.09 (SD = 0.69)	0.021
Mean values of family, friends, teachers factor	2.87 (SD = 0.72)	3.16 (SD = 0.66)	0.001

Testing differences in mean scores of influencing factors by gender reveals that the mean scores of influencing factors among female students are higher than those among male students, and this difference is statistically significant.

TABLE 5. Mean values of factors influencing perception of Social work profession by field of study

	Basic Sciences major	Natural Sciences major	Social Sciences major	p-value
Mean value of individual factor	3.04 (SD = 0.69)	2.93 (SD = 0.79)	3.28 (SD = 0.60)	0.003
Mean value of profession-specific factor	3.03 (SD = 0.68)	2.84 (SD = 0.78)	3.11 (SD = 0.64)	0.026
Mean value of family, friends, teachers factor	3.03 (SD = 0.68)	2.81 (SD = 0.76)	3.21 (SD = 0.60)	0.001

The mean score of the individual factor for students in the Social Sciences field is the highest at 3.28, followed by the Basic Sciences field at 3.04, and the Natural Sciences field at 2.93. It is evident that students in the Social Sciences field have a significantly higher mean score compared to those in the Basic and Natural Sciences field, with a *p-value* of 0.003.

The mean score of the profession-specific factor for students in the Social Sciences field is the highest at 3.11, followed by the Basic Sciences field at 3.03, and the Natural Sciences field at 2.84. Students in the Social Sciences field exhibit a significantly higher mean score compared to those in the Basic and Natural Sciences field, with a *p-value* of 0.026.

The mean score of the family, friends, teachers factor for students in the Social Sciences major is the highest at 3.21, followed by the Basic field at 3.03, and the Natural Sciences field at 2.81. Students in the Social Sciences field demonstrate a significantly higher mean score compared to those in the Basic and Natural Sciences field, with a *p-value* of 0.001.

DISCUSSIONS

The primary objective of the study was to (1) identify the factors influencing perceptions of the social work profession among high school students, including individual factors, profession-specific factors, and factors influenced by family, friends, and teachers, and (2) understand the differences in these factors among students based on gender and academic streams. The study identified three main factors influencing students' perceptions of the social work profession: individual factors (8 variables), profession-specific factors (9 variables), and factors influenced by family, friends, and teachers (8 variables). The reliability of each factor and the overall scale was assessed for internal consistency, with acceptable results indicated by Cronbach's alpha values, as supported by the literature. Furthermore, the results revealed differences in the influencing factors categorized by gender, specifically, female students scored higher on mean in these factors compared to male students. This finding suggests the continued importance of gender in career perceptions and decision-making among high school students. Moreover, students in the Social Sciences field demonstrated the highest mean scores in factors influencing perceptions, followed by students in the Basic and Natural Sciences fields. This observation aligns with the vocational landscape in Vietnam, where the social work profession is more aligned with students in the Social Sciences and Basic Sciences fields.

The study uncovered several significant findings. Firstly, the students' responses indicated the delineation of variables into three distinct factors influencing perceptions of the social work profession among high school students. This suggests that the questionnaire was well-designed and yielded results encompassing individual factors, profession-specific factors, and factors influenced by family, friends, and teachers. The correlation between individual and familial factors with career perceptions corroborates previous studies by Calaguas (2017) (Calaguas, 2017) and Le Thi Thuy (2016) (T. T. Le, 2016). Specifically, the profession-specific factor, particularly students' assessments of job prospects and salary considerations, had the most significant impact on students' perceptions, consistent with findings by Agarwala (2008) (Agarwala, 2008) and Gokuladas (2010) (Gokuladas, 2010). Secondly, the results also indicated gender differences in influencing factors, with female students scoring higher on these factors compared to male students. This finding underscores the continued importance of gender in career perceptions and decisions, aligning with traditional gender roles in professions such as healthcare, education, and social work (Kim & Reifel, 2010).

In the UK, Furness (2007) found that from 2002 to 2005, 83% of social work students were female (Furness, 2007), highlighting the ongoing significance of gender in career perceptions and decisions among high school students. In the current Vietnamese context, efforts towards gender equality in professions are being emphasized, necessitating strategies to enhance male students' awareness of the social work profession and attract them to consider it as a career option. Additionally, the results indicated that students in the Social Sciences field exhibited the highest mean scores in influencing factors, followed by the Basic Sciences field, and the lowest mean scores were observed in the Natural Sciences field. This evaluation is consistent with the vocational trends in Vietnam, where the social work profession aligns well with students in the Social Sciences and Basic fields.

Despite certain limitations, such as the restricted sample size, we hope to expand the scope of research in the future to include high schools in other provinces within the Mekong Delta region to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the factors influencing perceptions of the social work profession among high school students.

Nevertheless, these findings hold significant theoretical and practical implications. The study's findings offer a clearer understanding of the groups of factors influencing perceptions of the social work profession among high school students, encompassing individual factors, profession-specific factors, and factors influenced by family, friends, and teachers. Moreover, these findings have practical implications in the current Vietnamese context, where career guidance is becoming increasingly important and influential in shaping the career aspirations of high school students. Therefore, educational policymakers need to design and develop career guidance programs that can harness students' interests and aptitudes in different vocational fields, enabling students to make informed decisions aligned with their personal and professional goals.

CONCLUSION

Accurate career awareness for selecting a profession that aligns with one's personality is a crucial factor for high school students. It is essential to determine the factors upon which students' perceptions of the social work profession depend, so that counselors can provide tailored career guidance programs. The findings reveal three influencing factors: individual factors, profession-specific factors, and factors influenced by family, friends, and teachers. There are variations in the mean scores of these factors based on gender and academic streams. These findings highlight that a comprehensive understanding of the social work profession by students depends on multiple factors. Therefore, schools and families need to identify the factors influencing students' perceptions of this profession to provide suitable career guidance, enabling students to make informed decisions. This study is a novel exploration that specifically identifies factors influencing students' perceptions of the social work profession. The research findings serve as a foundation for further studies in the future.

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